

ON FUZZY SUPRA PSEUDO P-SPACES

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Abstract

In this paper, the notion of fuzzy supra pseudo P-spaces is introduced and characterized by means of fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets and fuzzy supra regular F_σ -sets. It is established that fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets in fuzzy supra pseudo P-spaces are fuzzy supra regular open but not fuzzy supra dense sets. The conditions for fuzzy supra pseudo P-spaces to become fuzzy supra σ -Baire spaces and fuzzy supra Volterra spaces are also established.

Keywords : Fuzzy supra dense set, Fuzzy supra G_δ -set, Fuzzy supra F_σ -sets, Fuzzy supra nowhere dense set, Fuzzy supra first category, Fuzzy supra second category, Fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set, Fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set, Fuzzy supra Baire spaces.

1. Introduction

In the year 1965, L. A.Zadeh [14] was first introduced the concept of fuzzy sets and fuzzy set operations in his classical paper. In 1968, the theory of fuzzy topological spaces was introduced and developed by C.L.Chang [4]. In 1983, Mashhour.A.S.et.al., [6] introduced and studied the concept of Supra topological spaces. In 1987, Abd El-monsef et.at [1] introduced the concepts of fuzzy supra topological as a natural generalization of the notion of supra topological spaces. In 1972, Mishra.A.K [7] introduced the concepts of P-spaces as a generalization of ω_α -additive spaces of Sikorski [11] and Cohen.L.W and Goffman.C [5]. The concept of P-spaces in fuzzy setting was introduced by Thangaraj.G and Balasubramanian.G [13]. The concept of fuzzy supra P-spaces and weak fuzzy supra P-spaces was introduced and studied by the author in [9,10].

In this paper, fuzzy supra pseudo spaces is introduced and characterized by means of fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets and fuzzy supra regular F_σ -sets. It is established that fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets in fuzzy supra pseudo P-spaces are fuzzy supra regular open but not fuzzy supra dense sets.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1 [1].

A collection S^* of fuzzy sets in a set M is called fuzzy supra topology on M if the following conditions are satisfied:

- 1) $\mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbf{1}$ belongs to S^* .
- 2) $g_\chi \in S^*$ for each $\chi \in \Lambda$ implies $(\bigvee_{\chi \in \Lambda} g_\chi) \in S^*$.

The pair (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra topological space. The elements of S^* are called fuzzy supra open sets and the complement of a fuzzy supra open set is called fuzzy supra closed set.

Definition: 2.2 [8]

Let (M, S^*) be a fuzzy supra topological space and B be a fuzzy set in M , then the fuzzy supra closure and fuzzy supra interior of B defined respectively as

$$cl^*(B) = \bigwedge \{ g / g \text{ is a fuzzy supra closed set in } U \text{ and } B \leq g \}$$

$$int^*(B) = \bigvee \{ g / g \text{ is a fuzzy supra open set in } U \text{ and } g \leq B \}$$

Definition: 2.3 [8]

Let (U, T) be a fuzzy topological space and S^* be a fuzzy supra topology on U . We call S^* a fuzzy supra topology associated with T if $T \leq S^*$.

Remark: 2.4 [1]

- (1). Every fuzzy topological space is a fuzzy supra topological space.
- (2). If (M, S^*) is an associated fuzzy supra topological space with the fuzzy topological space (M, S) , then every fuzzy open(closed) set in the fuzzy topological space (M, S) is fuzzy supra open(closed) set in the fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) .

Lemma 2.5 [4]

For a fuzzy set B in a fuzzy topological space M ,

$$(i) 1 - int^*(B) = cl^*(1 - B),$$

$$(ii) 1 - cl^*(B) = int^*(1 - B).$$

Definition 2.6 [3]

A fuzzy supra open set B in fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called fuzzy supra F_σ -set in (M, S^*) if $B = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (B_i)$, where $1 - B_i \in S^*$ for $i \in I$,

Definition 2.7 [3]

A fuzzy supra open set B in fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) if $B = \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} (B_i)$, where $B_i \in S^*$ for $i \in I$.

Definition 2.8 [3]

A fuzzy set B in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra dense set if there exists no fuzzy supra closed set D in (M, S^*) such that $B < D < 1$. That is, $cl^*(B) = 1$, in (M, S^*) .

Definition 2.9 [3]

A fuzzy set B in fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra nowhere dense set if there exists no non-zero fuzzy supra open set A in (M, S^*) such that $A < cl^*(B)$. That is, $int^*cl^*(B) = 0$, in (M, S^*) .

Definition 2.10 [3]

A fuzzy set B in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra first category set if $B = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (B_i)$, where (B_i) 's are fuzzy supra nowhere dense set in (M, S^*) . Any other fuzzy set in (M, S^*) is said to be fuzzy supra second category space.

Definition 2.11 [2]

A fuzzy set B in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra boundary of B is defined as $Bd(B) = cl^*(B) \wedge cl^*(1 - B)$. Obviously $Bd(B)$ is a fuzzy supra closed set in (M, S^*) .

Definition 2.12 [3]

A fuzzy set B in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra simply-open set if $Bd(B)$ is a fuzzy supra no-where dense set in (M, S^*) . That is., B is an fuzzy supra simply-open set in (M, S^*) if $int^*cl^*[cl^*(B) \wedge cl^*(1 - B)] = 0$ in (M, S^*) .

Definition 2.13 [2]

A fuzzy set B in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra semi-open set in (M, S^*) if $B \leq cl^*int^*(B)$; fuzzy supra semi-closed set in (M, S^*) if $int^*cl^*(B) \leq B$.

Definition 2.14 [3]

A fuzzy set B in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set if there exists a non-zero fuzzy open set B in (M, S^*) such that $B < cl^*(B)$. That is., $int^*cl^*(B) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) .

Definition 2.15. [11]

A fuzzy set B in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra regular-open set if $B = \text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(B)$ and fuzzy supra regular closed set if $B = \text{cl}^* \text{int}^*(B)$ in (M, S^*) .

Theorem 2.1. [3]

If A is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) if and only if $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (M, S^*) .

Theorem 2.2. [10]

If A is a fuzzy supra residual set in an fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then there exists a fuzzy supra G_δ -set B in (M, S^*) such that $B \leq A$.

Theorem 2.3. [3]

If A is a fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense set in an fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) , then A is a fuzzy supra first category set in (M, S^*) .

Theorem 2.4. [9]

A fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P-space if and only if $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (A_i)$, where (A_i) 's are fuzzy supra regular closed sets in (M, S^*) .

Theorem 2.5. [3]

If A is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in an fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) such that $\text{cl}^*(A) = 1$, then A is a fuzzy supra residual set in (M, S^*) .

Theorem 2.6. [3]

Let (M, S^*) be a fuzzy supra topological space. Then the following are Equivalent.

- (1) (M, S^*) is an fuzzy supra Baire space.
- (2) $\text{int}^*(A) = 0$; for every fuzzy supra first category set A in (M, S^*)
- (3) $\text{cl}^*(B) = 1$; for every fuzzy supra residual set B in (M, S^*) .

Theorem 2.7. [3]

If A is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) , then there exists a fuzzy supra regular closed set B in (M, S^*) such that $B \leq \text{cl}^*(A)$.

Theorem 2.8. [9]

If A is a fuzzy supra residual set in the fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) in which fuzzy supra first category sets are not fuzzy supra dense sets, then A is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Theorem 2.9. [3]

If a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set A is a fuzzy supra dense set in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) , then A is a fuzzy supra residual set in (M, S^*) .

Theorem 2.10. [3]

If $A \leq B$ and B is a fuzzy supra first category set in the fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) , then A is also a fuzzy supra first category set in (M, S^*) .

Theorem 2.11. [3]

If A is a fuzzy supra Baire dense set in an fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) , then there exists a fuzzy supra second category set C such that $C \leq A$ in (M, S^*) .

Theorem 2.12. [3]

If A is a fuzzy supra Baire dense set in the fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) , then there exist fuzzy supra second category sets C_1 and C_2 in (M, S^*) such that $C_1 < A < C_2$.

Theorem 2.13. [3]

If A is a fuzzy supra Baire dense set in the fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) , then there is no fuzzy supra F_σ -set B , with $\text{int}(B) = 0$ in (M, S^*) such that $A < B$.

Theorem 2.14. [3]

If A is a fuzzy supra Baire dense set in the fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) , then there is no fuzzy supra residual set C in (M, S^*) such that $1 - A > C$.

Theorem 2.15. [3]

Let (M, S^*) be the fuzzy supra topological space. Then, the following are Equivalent.

- (1) (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra Baire space.

(2) Each non-zero fuzzy supra open set is a fuzzy supra second category set in (M, S^*) :

Theorem 2.16. [3]

If (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra Baire space, then (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra second category space.

Theorem 2.17. [3]

If (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra second category space, then (M, S^*) is not a fuzzy supra almost irresolvable space.

Theorem 2.18. [3]

If the fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra σ -Baire space, then (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra Volterra space.

3. Fuzzy supra Pseudo P-Spaces

Definition 3.1.

Let (M, S^*) be a fuzzy supra topological space. Then, (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space if it is both a fuzzy supra almost P-space and weak fuzzy supra P-space.

Example 3.1.

Let $M = \{a, b, c\}$. Let $I = [0, 1]$. The fuzzy supra sets A, B, C, D and E are defined as follows:

$A: M \rightarrow I$ is defined by $A(a)=0.6; A(b)=0.4; A(c)=0.6$,

$B: M \rightarrow I$ is defined by $B(a)=0.5; B(b)=0.5; B(c)=0.5$,

$C: M \rightarrow I$ is defined by $C(a)=0.4; C(b)=0.5; C(c)=0.6$,

$D: M \rightarrow I$ is defined by $D(a)=0.4; D(b)=0.6; D(c)=0.4$,

$E: M \rightarrow I$ is defined by $E(a)=0.5; E(b)=0.6; E(c)=0.4$.

Then, $S^* = \{0, A, B, D, A \vee B, A \vee D, B \vee D, A \wedge B, A \wedge D, B \wedge D, 1\}$ is a fuzzy supra topology on M . By computation, $cl^*(A) = 1 - D = A$; $cl^*(B) = 1 - B = B$; $cl^*(D) = 1 - A = D$; $cl^*(A \vee B) = 1 - [B \wedge D] = A \vee B$; $cl^*(A \vee D) = 1 - [A \wedge D] = A \vee D$; $cl^*(B \vee D) = 1 - [A \wedge B] = B \vee D$; $cl^*(A \wedge B) = 1 - [B \vee D] = A \wedge B$; $cl^*(C) = A \vee D$; $cl^*(A \wedge D) = 1 - [A \vee D] = A \wedge D$; $cl^*(B \wedge D) = 1 - [A \vee B] = B \wedge D$; $cl^*(E) = B \vee D$. Also $int^*[cl^*(A)] = int^*[A] = A$; $int^*[cl^*(B)] = int^*[B] = B$; $int^*[cl^*(D)] = int^*[D] = D$; $int^*[cl^*(A \vee B)] = int^*[A \vee B] = A \vee B$; $int^*[cl^*(A \vee D)] = int^*[A \vee D] = A \vee D$; $int^*[cl^*(B \vee D)] = int^*[B \vee D] = B \vee D$; $int^*[cl^*(A \wedge B)] = int^*[A \wedge B] = A \wedge B$; $int^*[cl^*(A \wedge D)] = int^*[A \wedge D] = A \wedge D$; $int^*[cl^*(B \wedge D)] = int^*[B \wedge D] = B \wedge D$; $int^*[cl^*(C)] = int^*[A \vee D] = A \vee D \neq C$; $int^*[cl^*(E)] = int^*[B \vee D] = B \vee D \neq E$. Thus $A, B, D, A \vee B, A \vee D, B \vee D, A \wedge B, A \wedge D, B \wedge D$, are fuzzy supra regular open sets in (M, S^*) . But C and E are not fuzzy supra regular open sets in (M, S^*) . Now $A \wedge B \wedge D \wedge (A \vee B) \wedge (A \vee D) \wedge (B \vee D) \wedge (A \wedge B) \wedge (A \wedge D) \wedge (B \wedge D) = A \wedge D$ and $A \wedge D$ is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M, S^*) implies that (M, S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P-space.

Also, $A \wedge D = A \wedge B \wedge D \wedge [A \vee B] \wedge [A \vee D] \wedge [B \vee D] \wedge [A \wedge B] \wedge [B \wedge D]$ and hence $A \wedge D$ is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) and $int^*(A \wedge D) = A \wedge D \neq 0$, implies that (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-spaces. Thus (M, S^*) is Both a fuzzy supra almost P-space and weak fuzzy supra P-spaces and hence (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra Pseudo P-spaces.

Proposition 3.1.

Let (M, S^*) be a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space. Then

- (i) For a fuzzy supra G_δ -set A in (M, S^*) , $int^*(A) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) ,
- (ii) For a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set B in (M, S^*) , B is the fuzzy supra regular open set in (M, S^*) such that $cl^*(B) \neq 1$ in (X, T) .

Proof.

(i). Let A be a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Being a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space, (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space and then for the fuzzy supra G_δ -set

$A, \text{int}^*(A) \neq 0, \text{in } (M, S^*)$.

(ii) Being a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space, (M, S^*) is the weak fuzzy supra P-space and then the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set $B (\neq 1)$ is the fuzzy supra regular open set in (M, S^*) and hence $\text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(B) = B$. Then, $\text{cl}^*(B) \neq 1$ [for, otherwise if $\text{cl}^*(B) = 1$, then $\text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(B) = \text{int}^*(1) = 1 \neq B$, a contradiction]. Hence the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set B is not a fuzzy supra dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.2.

Let (M, S^*) be a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space. Then

- (i) For a fuzzy supra F_σ -set C in (M, S^*) , $\text{cl}^*(C) \neq 1, \text{in } (M, S^*)$.
- (ii) For a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set B in (M, S^*) , B is a fuzzy supra regular closed set in (M, S^*) and $\text{int}^*(B) \neq 0, \text{in } (M, S^*)$.

Proof.

(i). Let C be a fuzzy supra F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Then, $1-C$ is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space, by Proposition 3.1 (i), for the fuzzy supra G_δ -set $1-C$ in (M, S^*) , $\text{int}^*(1-C) \neq 0$. Then, $1 - \text{cl}^*(C) = \text{int}^*(1-C)$ implies that $1 - \text{cl}^*(C) \neq 0$. Thus $\text{cl}^*(C) \neq 1, \text{in } (X, T)$.

(ii). Let $B (\neq 0)$ be a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Then, $1-B$ is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space, by Proposition 3.1 (ii), $1-B$ is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M, S^*) and thus B is a fuzzy supra regular closed set in (M, S^*) . Then, $\text{cl}^* \text{int}^*(B) = B$. This implies that $\text{int}^*(B) \neq 0$ [for, otherwise if $\text{int}^*(B) = 0$ and then $\text{cl}^* \text{int}^*(B) = 0 \neq B$, a contradiction]. Hence, B is a fuzzy supra regular closed set and $\text{int}^*(B) \neq 0, \text{in } (M, S^*)$.

Proposition 3.3.

If D is a fuzzy supra residual set in the fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M, S^*) , then $\text{int}^*(D) \neq 0, \text{in } (M, S^*)$.

Proof.

Suppose that D is a fuzzy supra residual set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space, (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space and then, by Theorem 2.2, there exists a fuzzy supra G_δ -set C in (M, S^*) such that $C \leq D$. Because (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space, $\text{int}^*(C) \neq 0, \text{in } (M, S^*)$. Now $C \leq D$, implies that $\text{int}^*(C) \leq \text{int}^*(D)$ and thus $\text{int}^*(D) \neq 0, \text{in } (M, S^*)$.

Proposition 3.4.

If A is a fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense set in the fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M, S^*) ,

- (i). A is not a fuzzy supra dense set in (M, S^*) .
- (ii). $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

(i). Suppose that A is a fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense set in (M, S^*) . Then, by Theorem 2.3, A is a fuzzy supra first category set in (M, S^*) and then $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra residual set in (M, S^*) . Because (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space, by Proposition 3.3, $\text{int}^*(1-A) \neq 0, \text{in } (X, T)$. Now by lemma 2.5, $\text{int}^*(1-A) = 1 - \text{cl}^*(A)$ and then $1 - \text{cl}^*(A) \neq 0, \text{in } (M, S^*)$. Thus, $\text{cl}^*(A) \neq 1$ in (M, S^*) . Hence, A is not a fuzzy supra dense set in (M, S^*) .

(ii). Since A is a fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense set in (M, S^*) , A is a fuzzy supra F_σ -set in (M, S^*) with $\text{int}^*(A) = 0$. Now $\text{cl}^*(1-A) = 1 - \text{int}^*(A) = 1 - 0 = 1$ and hence $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra dense set in (X, T) .

The following proposition establishes the irresolvability of a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space.

Proposition 3.5.

If A is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in the fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M, S^*) with $cl^*(A) = 1$, then (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra irresolvable space.

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) with $cl^*(A) = 1$. Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space, by Proposition 3.1 (i), for the fuzzy supra G_δ -set A , $int^*(A) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) . Also $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra F_σ -set in (M, S^*) with $int^*(1-A) = 1 - cl^*(A) = 0$. Thus, $1-A$ is an fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense set in (M, S^*) . Because (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space, by Proposition 3.4 (ii), $cl^*(1-[1-A]) = cl^*(A) = 1$, and $cl^*(1-A) = 1 - int^*(A) \neq 1$, in (X, T) . Thus, for the fuzzy supra dense set A , $cl^*(1 - A) \neq 1$, in (M, S^*) , shows that (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra irresolvable space.

Proposition 3.6.

If (A_i) 's are fuzzy supra semi-open sets in the fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M, S^*) , Then $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} cl^*(A_i)$ is a fuzzy supra regular closed set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Suppose that (A_i) 's are fuzzy supra semi-open sets in (M, S^*) . Then, $[cl^*(A_i)]$'s are fuzzy supra regular closed sets in (M, S^*) . Because (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space, (M, S^*) is the weak fuzzy supra P-space and then by Theorem 2.4, $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} cl^*(A_i)$ is a fuzzy supra regular closed set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.7.

If D is a fuzzy supra residual set in a fuzzy supra P-space (M, S^*) , then there exists a fuzzy supra Baire set B in (M, S^*) such that $B \leq D$.

Proof.

Suppose that D is a fuzzy supra residual set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra P-space, (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space and then, by Theorem 2.2, there exists a fuzzy supra G_δ -set C in (M, S^*) such that $B \leq D$. Now $CAD \leq D$ in (M, S^*) . Because (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra P-space, the fuzzy supra G_δ -set C is a fuzzy supra open in (M, S^*) . Let $B = C \wedge D$. Then, B is a fuzzy supra Baire set in (M, S^*) . Thus, there exists a fuzzy supra Baire set B in (M, S^*) such that $B \leq D$.

Proposition 3.8.

If B is a fuzzy supra first category set in the fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M, S^*) , then $cl^*(B) \neq 1$, in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let B be a fuzzy supra first category set in (M, S^*) . Then, $1-B$ is a fuzzy supra residual set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space, by the Proposition 3.3, $int^*(1-B) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) . Then $1 - cl^*(B) \neq 0$ and thus $cl^*(B) \neq 1$, in (M, S^*) .

The following proposition gives the condition for the fuzzy supra pseudo P-spaces to become fuzzy supra Baire and fuzzy supra irresolvable spaces.

Proposition 3.9.

If A is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in the fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M, S^*) with $cl^*(A) = 1$, then (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra Baire and fuzzy supra irresolvable space.

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) with $cl^*(A) = 1$. Then, by Theorem 2.5, A is a fuzzy supra residual set in (M, S^*) . Thus for the residual set A , $cl^*(A) = 1$, in (M, S^*) . Then, by Theorem 2.6, (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra Baire space. Also since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space, by Proposition 3.5, (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra irresolvable space. Hence (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra Baire and fuzzy supra irresolvable space.

Proposition 3.10.

If B is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M, S^*) , then B is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let B be a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space, by Proposition 3.1(i), $\text{int}^*(B) \neq \emptyset$ in (M, S^*) . Then, $\text{int}^*(B) \subseteq \text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(B)$, implies that $\text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(B) \neq \emptyset$ in (M, S^*) . Hence B is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.11.

If B is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M, S^*) , then there exist a fuzzy supra regular closed set E in (M, S^*) such that $E \subseteq \text{cl}^*(B)$.

Proof.

Let B be a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space, by Proposition 3.10, B is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) . By Theorem 2.7, for the fuzzy supra G_δ -set B in (M, S^*) , there exist a fuzzy supra regular closed set E in (M, S^*) such that $E \subseteq \text{cl}^*(B)$.

Proposition 3.12.

If A is a fuzzy supra residual set in a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M, S^*) , then A is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra residual set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space, by Proposition 3.8, fuzzy supra first category sets are not fuzzy supra dense sets in (M, S^*) . Then, by Theorem 2.8, the fuzzy supra residual set A is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.13.

If A is a fuzzy supra residual set in a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M, S^*) , then there exist a fuzzy supra regular closed set E in (M, S^*) such that $E \subseteq \text{cl}^*(A)$.

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra residual set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space, by Proposition 3.12, A is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) . By Theorem 2.7, for the fuzzy supra residual set A in (M, S^*) , there exist a fuzzy supra regular closed set E in (M, S^*) such that $E \subseteq \text{cl}^*(A)$.

Proposition 3.14.

If A is a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in a fuzzy supra extremally disconnected and fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M, S^*) , then A is a fuzzy supra clopen set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (X, T) . Then, $A = \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} \text{cl}^*(C_i)$ where $C_i \in S^*$. Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra extremally disconnected space, closure of every fuzzy supra open set is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) and hence $[\text{cl}^*(C_i)]$'s are fuzzy supra open sets in (M, S^*) . Then, $A = \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} \text{cl}^*(C_i)$, is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) and thus $\text{int}^*(A) = A$. Also since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space, by Proposition 3.2(ii), the fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set A is a fuzzy supra regular closed set in (M, S^*) and hence $\text{cl}^* \text{int}^*(A) = A$. Then, $\text{cl}^*(A) = \text{cl}^* \text{int}^*(A) = A$ and thus A is a fuzzy supra closed set in (M, S^*) . Therefore A is a fuzzy supra clopen set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.15.

If A is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in a fuzzy supra extremally disconnected and fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M, S^*) , then A is a fuzzy supra clopen set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

The proof follows from the proposition 3.14 and the Theorem 2.1.

Proposition 3.16.

If A is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in a fuzzy supra pseudo P -space (M, S^*) , then A is not a fuzzy supra residual set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P -space, by Proposition 3.1(ii), the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set A is the fuzzy supra regular open set in (M, S^*) such that $cl^*(B) \neq 1$ in (M, S^*) . That is, A is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set which is not fuzzy supra dense in (M, S^*) . Then, by Theorem 2.9, A is not an fuzzy supra residual set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.17.

If C is a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in a fuzzy supra pseudo P -space (M, S^*) , then C is not a fuzzy supra first category set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let C be a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Then, $1-C$ is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P -space, by Proposition 3.16, $1-C$ is not a fuzzy supra residual set in (M, S^*) and hence C is not a fuzzy supra first category set in (M, S^*) .

The following proposition establishes that fuzzy supra regular F_σ -sets are fuzzy supra Baire dense sets in fuzzy supra pseudo P -spaces.

Proposition 3.18.

If C is a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in a fuzzy supra pseudo P -space (M, S^*) , then C is a fuzzy supra Baire dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let C be a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Suppose that there is a fuzzy supra first category set B in (M, S^*) such that $C < B < 1$. Then, by Theorem 2.10, C will be a fuzzy supra first category set in (M, S^*) which is a contradiction, since fuzzy supra regular F_σ -sets are not fuzzy supra first category sets in fuzzy supra pseudo P -spaces [by Proposition 3.17]. Hence there is no fuzzy supra first category set B in (M, S^*) such that $C < B < 1$. Thus, C is a fuzzy supra Baire dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.19.

If C is a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in a fuzzy supra pseudo P -space (M, S^*) , then there exists a fuzzy supra second category set B such that $B \leq C$ in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let C be a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P -space, by Proposition 3.18, the fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set C is a fuzzy supra Baire dense set in (M, S^*) and then, by Theorem 2.11, there exists a fuzzy supra second category set B such that $B \leq C$ in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.20.

If C is a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in a fuzzy supra pseudo P -space (M, S^*) , then there exist fuzzy supra second category sets B_1 and B_2 in (M, S^*) such that $B_1 < C < B_2$.

Proof.

Let C be a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P -space, by Proposition 3.18, the fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set C is a fuzzy supra Baire dense set in (M, S^*) and then, by Theorem 2.12, there exist fuzzy supra second category sets B_1 and

B_2 in (M, S^*) such that $B_1 < C < B_2$.

Proposition 3.21.

If C is a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M, S^*) , then there is no fuzzy supra F_σ -set B , with $\text{int}^*(B) = 0$ in (M, S^*) such that $C < B$.

Proof.

Let C be a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space, by Proposition 3.18, the fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set C is a fuzzy supra Baire dense set in (M, S^*) and then, by Theorem 2.13, there is no fuzzy supra F_σ -set B , with $\text{int}^*(B) = 0$ in (M, S^*) such that $C < B$.

Proposition 3.22.

If C is a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M, S^*) , then there is no fuzzy supra residual set B in (M, S^*) such that $1 - C > B$.

Proof.

Let C be a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space, by Proposition 3.18, the fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set C is a fuzzy supra Baire dense set in (M, S^*) and then, by Theorem 2.14, there is no fuzzy supra residual set B in (M, S^*) such that $1 - C > B$.

Proposition 3.23.

If C is a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M, S^*) , then there is no fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense set B in (M, S^*) such that $C < B$.

Proof.

Let C be a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space, by Proposition 3.21, there is no fuzzy supra F_σ -set B , with $\text{int}^*(B) = 0$ in (M, S^*) such that $C < B$. Since a fuzzy supra F_σ -set B , with $\text{int}^*(B) = 0$ is a fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense set in (M, S^*) , then there is no fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense set B in (M, S^*) such that $C < B$.

Proposition 3.24.

If B is a fuzzy supra B -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M, S^*) , then $B \leq C$, where C is a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let B be a fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense set in (M, S^*) . It is claimed that $B \leq C$, where C is a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Assume the contrary. Suppose that $C < B$. Then, for the fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set C in the fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M, S^*) , there is a fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense set B in (M, S^*) such that $C < B$, which is a contradiction by Proposition 3.23. Thus our claim that $C < B$, does not hold and hence if B is a fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense set in (M, S^*) , then $B \leq C$, where C is a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.25.

If A is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in the fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M, S^*) , then there is no fuzzy supra G_δ -set D with $\text{cl}^*(D) = 1$, in (M, S^*) such that $A > D$.

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Suppose that there is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set D with $\text{cl}^*(D) = 1$, in (M, S^*) such that $A > D$. Then $1 - A < 1 - D$ in (M, S^*) and $\text{int}^*(1 - D) = 1 - \text{cl}^*(D) = 1 - 1 = 0$. Since A is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set, by Theorem 2.1, $1 - A$ is a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . If $1 - D = B$, then B is a fuzzy supra F_σ -set and thus for the fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set $1 - A$ in the fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M, S^*) , there is a fuzzy supra F_σ -set B with $\text{int}^*(B) = 0$, in (M, S^*) such that $1 - A < B$,

which is a contradiction by the Proposition 3.21. Hence there is no fuzzy supra G_δ -set D with $cl^*(D)=1$, in (M,S^*) such that $A>D$.

Proposition 3.26.

If D is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set with $cl^*(D)=1$, in a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M,S^*) , then $A\leq D$, where A is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M,S^*) .

Proof.

Let D be a fuzzy supra G_δ -set with $cl^*(D) = 1$, in (M,S^*) . It is claimed that $A\leq D$, where A is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M,S^*) . Assume the contrary. Suppose that $D<A$. Then, for the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set A in the fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M,S^*) , there is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set D with $cl^*(D) = 1$, in (M,S^*) such that $D<A$, which is a contradiction by Proposition 3.25. Thus our claim that $D<A$, does not hold and hence for the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set A in (M,S^*) , $A \leq D$, where A is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in the fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M,S^*) .

Proposition 3.27.

If D is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set with $cl^*(D)=1$, in a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M,S^*) , then $A\leq D$, where A is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M,S^*) and

- (i). A is not a fuzzy supra residual set in (M,S^*) .
- (ii). D is a fuzzy supra residual set in (M,S^*) .

Proof.

Let D be a fuzzy supra G_δ -set with $cl^*(D)=1$, in (M,S^*) . Since (M,S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space, by the Proposition 3.26, $A \leq D$ where A is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (X, T) .

- (i). By Proposition 3.16, the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set A is not a fuzzy supra residual set in (M,S^*) .
- (ii). Since D is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set with $cl^*(D) = 1$ in (M,S^*) , by Theorem 2.5, D is a fuzzy supra residual set in (M,S^*) .

4. Fuzzy Supra Pseudo P-Spaces and Other Fuzzy Supra Topological Spaces

The following propositions gives conditions for fuzzy supra pseudo P-space to become fuzzy supra Baire spaces, fuzzy supra second category spaces and fuzzy supra almost irresolvable spaces.

Proposition 4.1.

If there exists a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set C in the fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M,S^*) such that $C<B$, for a fuzzy supra open set B in (M,S^*) , then (M,S^*) is a fuzzy supra Baire space.

Proof.

Let C be a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (M,S^*) . Since (M,S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P-space, by Proposition 3.18, the fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set C is a fuzzy supra Baire dense set in (M,S^*) . By hypothesis, $C<B$, where B is a fuzzy supra open set in (M,S^*) . Since C is a fuzzy supra Baire dense set in (M,S^*) , there is no fuzzy supra first category set D in (M,S^*) such that $C<D<1$. Since $C<B$, B cannot be a fuzzy supra first category set in (M,S^*) and hence the fuzzy supra open set B must be a fuzzy supra second category set in (M,S^*) . This implies that the fuzzy supra open set in (M,S^*) , is a fuzzy supra second category sets in (M,S^*) . Hence by Theorem 2.15, (M,S^*) is a fuzzy supra Baire space.

Proposition 4.2.

If there exists a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set C in the fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M,S^*) such that $C<B$, for a fuzzy supra open set B in (M,S^*) , then (M,S^*) is a fuzzy supra second category space.

Proof.

The Proof follows from the Proposition 4.1 and the Theorem 2.16.

Proposition 4.3.

If there exists a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set C in the fuzzy supra pseudo P -space (M, S^*) such that $C < B$, for a fuzzy supra open set B in (M, S^*) , then (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost irresolvable space.

Proof.

The Proof follows from the Proposition 4.2 and the Theorem 2.17.

Proposition 4.4.

If there exists a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set A for each fuzzy supra closed set D in the fuzzy supra pseudo P -space (M, S^*) such that $D < A$, then (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra Baire space.

Proof.

Let D be a fuzzy supra closed set in (M, S^*) . Suppose that there exists a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set A in (M, S^*) such that $D < A$. Then $1-A < 1-D$, in (M, S^*) . Since D is a fuzzy supra closed set in (M, S^*) , $1-D$ is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) . Also $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Thus, for the fuzzy supra open set $1-D$, there exists a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set $1-A$ such that $1-A < 1-D$, in (M, S^*) . Then, by Proposition 4.1, the fuzzy supra pseudo P -space (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra Baire space.

Proposition 4.5.

If there exists a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set A for each fuzzy supra closed set D in the fuzzy supra pseudo P -space (M, S^*) such that $D < A$, then (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra second category space.

Proof.

The proof follows from the Proposition 4.4 and the Theorem 2.16.

Proposition 4.6.

If there exists a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set A for each fuzzy supra closed set D in the fuzzy supra pseudo P -space (M, S^*) such that $D < A$, then (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost irresolvable space.

Proof.

The proof follows from the Proposition 4.5 and the Theorem 2.17.

The following proposition gives condition for fuzzy supra pseudo P -spaces to become fuzzy supra σ -Baire spaces.

Proposition 4.7.

If $\text{int}^*[\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (C_i)] = 0$, where (C_i) 's are fuzzy supra regular F_σ -sets in the fuzzy supra pseudo P -space (M, S^*) , then (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra σ -Baire space.

Proof.

Suppose that (B_i) 's are fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense sets in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra pseudo P -space, by Proposition 3.24, $B_i \leq C_i$, where (C_i) 's are the fuzzy supra regular F_σ -sets in (M, S^*) . This implies that $\text{int}^*[\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (B_i)] \leq \text{int}^*[\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (C_i)]$. By hypothesis, $\text{int}^*[\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (C_i)] = 0$, and hence $\text{int}^*[\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (B_i)] = 0$, where (B_i) 's are fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense sets in (X, T) . Thus (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra σ -Baire space.

Proposition 4.8.

If $\text{cl}^*[\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} (A_i)] = 1$, where (A_i) 's are fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets in the fuzzy supra Pseudo P -space (M, S^*) , then (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra σ -Baire space.

Proof.

Suppose that $\text{cl}^*[\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty}(A_i)]=1$, where (A_i) 's are fuzzy supra regular G_{δ} -sets in (M, S^*) . Now $1-\text{cl}^*[\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty}(A_i)]=0$ and then $\text{int}^*[1-(\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty}(A_i))]=0$, and $\text{int}^*[\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(1-A_i)]=0$, where $(1-A_i)$'s are fuzzy supra regular F_{σ} -sets in the fuzzy supra pseudo P-space (M, S^*) . Thus, by Proposition 4.7, (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra σ -Baire space.

Proposition 4.9.

If $\text{cl}^*[\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty}(A_i)]=1$, where (A_i) 's are fuzzy supra regular G_{δ} -sets in the fuzzy supra Pseudo P-space (M, S^*) , then (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra Volterra space.

Proof.

The proof follows from the Proposition 4.8 and the Theorem 2.18.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, the notion of fuzzy supra pseudo P-spaces is introduced and It is established that fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense sets and fuzzy supra first category sets in fuzzy supra pseudo P-spaces are not fuzzy supra dense sets. The conditions for fuzzy supra pseudo P-spaces to become fuzzy supra Baire spaces and fuzzy supra irresolvable spaces are obtained. It is established that fuzzy supra regular F_{σ} -sets in fuzzy supra pseudo P-spaces are not fuzzy supra first category sets and fuzzy supra regular F_{σ} -sets in fuzzy supra pseudo P-spaces, are fuzzy supra Baire dense sets. The conditions for fuzzy supra pseudo P-spaces to become fuzzy supra σ -Baire spaces and Volterra spaces are also obtained.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this article.

References

- [1]. Abd El-Monsef, M. E. and Ramadan, A. E.,(1987), On fuzzy supra topological spaces, Indian J. Pure Appl.Math., Vol.18(4), 322-329.
- [2]. Ahmed S, Chandra Chetia B (2014), On Certain properties of fuzzy supra semi open sets, International Journal of Fuzzy Mathematics and Systems, Vol.4(1), 93-98.
- [3]. Celine A (2023), A Study on Fuzzy Supra Baire Spaces, Ph.D Thesis, Thiruvalluvar University, Tamilnadu, India.
- [4]. Chang. C.L. (1968), Fuzzy topological spaces, Journal of Mathematical Analysis and applications, Vol.24, 182-190.
- [5]. Cohen.L.W and Goffman.C (1949), A theory of transfinite convergence, Trans. Amer. Math. Soc., Vol.66, 65-74.
- [6]. Mashhour A.S., Allam A.A., Mahmoud F.S and Khedr F.H., (1983), On Supra Topological Spaces, Indian J. Pure and Appl. Math., Vol.4(14), 502-510.
- [7]. Mishra.A.K.,(1972), Topological view of P-spaces, Gen. Topology Appl. Vol.2(4), 349-362.
- [8] Sahidul Ahmed and Biman Chandra Chetia (2014), On Certain Properties of Fuzzy Supra Semi open Sets, International Journal of Fuzzy Mathematics and Systems, Vol.4(1), 93-98.
- [9] Selvakumar K, Mahaboob Hassain Sherieff K and Vinothkumar A (2023), On Fuzzy Supra P-space, Stochastic Modelling and Computational Sciences Vol.3(1), 237-243.
- [10] Selvakumar K, Mahaboob Hassain Sherieff K and Vinothkumar A (2025), On Weak Fuzzy Supra P-space, High Technology Letters, Vol.31(7), 1-10.
- [11] Sikorski.R (1950), Remarks on spaces of high power, Fund. Math. Vol.37, 125-136.

- [12] Srikiruthika J, Kalaichelvi A., Fuzzy Supra Regular Open Sets, International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics, Vol.119(15) (2018), 731-735.
- [13] Thangaraj.G and Balasubramanian.G (2001), On Fuzzy Basically Disconnected Spaces, J.Fuzzy Math. Vol.9(1), 103-110.
- [14]. Zadeh. L.A (1965), Fuzzy sets, Informatics and Control, Vol.8, 338-353.